

一种用于验证单程光速是否相同的实验装置

An experimental setup to verify whether the speed of light is the same

摘要: 要想对空间绝对参考系（以太）进行测量，最好的测量方法就是，直接对不同方向光线的单向传播速度的测量，所以在这里专门设计了一个全新的对光速和“以太”测量，以及验证不同方向单程光速是否相同的实验装置。

Abstract: In order to measure the spatial absolute reference frame (aether), the best measurement method is to directly measure the one-direction propagation speed of light in different directions, so here specially designed a new speed of light and "aether" measurement, and to verify whether the speed of light in different directions is the same experimental device.

关键词: 物理实验；以太测量；光速测量；地球绝对速度测量；实验装置；以太；时空绝对参考系；绝对参考系；光速叠加

Key words: physical experiment; ether measurement; light velocity measurement; earth absolute velocity measurement; experimental device; ether; space-time absolute reference frame; absolute reference frame; light speed superposition

0 引言

0 Introduction

在《三元平衡定律》一书中有关对“迈克尔逊—莫雷实验”的分析中，我们通过电磁波的三元平衡系统的特征，对“迈克尔逊—莫雷实验”用来测量“以太”进行了一个较为全面的分析。分析的结论就是，利用两束光的光程变化，其实并不能使这两束光的干涉条纹产生足以使人察觉的干涉条纹的变化。

In the analysis of the Michelson-Morley experiment in the law of ternary equilibrium, we make a more comprehensive analysis of the Michelson-Morley experiment used to measure the aether through the characteristics of the ternary equilibrium system of electromagnetic waves. The conclusion of the analysis is that the change of the two light lines does not actually make the interference stripes of the two lights change enough to be detected.

1 实验装置的原理

1 Principles of the experimental setup

1.1 单程光速测量的实验装置原理示意图

1.1 Schematic diagram of the experimental device for one-way light speed measurement

这个单程光速测量的实验装置,是由一个带孔的挡板和一個转轴以及一个特殊的反光鏡三部分組成。这三部分是一个固定的整体,当转轴转动的时候,挡板和反光鏡也会同步转动。

This experimental device for one-way light speed measurement consists of a baffle with a hole, a rotating shaft and a special reflector. These three parts are a fixed whole, and when the rotating shaft rotates, the baffle and the mirror also rotate synchronously.

其工作的基本原理就是,当整个实验装置静止时,光源 a 通过发射一束光,这束光从挡板 b 的小孔穿过之后射到反光鏡 c,最后在由反光鏡 c 将光线反射到投射点 d。

The basic principle of its work is that when the whole experimental device is still, the light source a emits a beam of light that passes through the hole of the baffle b to the mirror c, and finally reflects the light to the projection point d by the mirror c.

当确定好实验装置静止时的投射点 d 之后,然后转动整个实验装置。当实验装置转动起来之后,光源 a 发出的光线就会在挡板 b 的高速转动下,被切割成一段一段的光线。

After determining the projection point d when the experimental device is stationary, the entire experimental device is then rotated. When the experimental device rotates, the light emitted by the light source a is cut into sections of light at the high rotation of the baffle b.

也就是说,当光线通过挡板 b 变成一段光线之后,这段光线从挡板 b 传递到反光鏡 c 需要一定的时间。但是在这段时间之内,整个实验装置依然会保持高速旋转,当这一段光线到达反光鏡 c 时,反光鏡就会转动一定的角度。当反光鏡转动一定角度之后,所以通过反光

镜 c 反射出去的光线，就会被反射到新的投射点 e。

That is, when the light becomes a ray of light through the baffle b, it takes some time for the light to pass from the baffle b to the mirror c. However, during this period, the entire experimental device will still rotate at a high speed, and when the section of light reaches the mirror c, the mirror will rotate at a certain Angle. When the mirror rotates at a certain Angle, the light reflected through the mirror c is reflected to the new projection point e.

1.2 测量方法

1.2 Measurement method

所以我们可以假设，挡板 b 到反光镜 c 的距离为 5m 远，实验装置的转动时的转速为 10000r/s，而光速为 300000km/s。如果不存在光速的速度叠加，那么通过相关的计算，会得出 c 到 d 的连接线与 c 到 e 的连接线之间，会形成一个 0.06° 的夹角。

So we can assume that the distance from the baffle b to the mirror c is 5m away, the rotation speed of the experimental device is 10,000 r/s, and the speed of light is 300,000 km/s. If there is no velocity superposition of the speed of light, then the relevant calculation would conclude that a 0.06 angle is formed between the connecting lines from c to d and those from c to e.

但是如果光速和地球运动的速度发生了速度叠加的话，那么光线从挡板 b 到反光镜 c 通过的时间就会不同，所以当光线到达反光镜 c 时，反光镜的旋转角度大小就会发生一定的变化。

However, if the speed of light and the speed of the earth's movement overlap, then the time of the light from the baffle b to the mirror c will be different, so when the light reaches the mirror c, the rotation angle of the mirror will change to some extent.

所以 c 到 d 的连接线与 c 到 e 的连接线之间的这个角度，就会在 0.06° 上下存在一个微小的变化。

So this angle between the c to d connections and the c to e connections makes a slight change around 0.06.

1.3 一些需要注意的事项以及实验装置的缺陷

1.3 Some matters needing attention and the defects of the experimental device

每次做这个实验时，可以让实验装置完全保持之前的状态，利用地球的自转，使地球的绝对运动方向与光线的方向呈现不同情况的光速叠加状态，所以需要在不同的时间反复多次实验。但是需要注意的是，每一次实验中实验装置的转速需要相同。

Every time this experiment is done, the experimental device can completely maintain the previous state. Using the rotation of the earth, the absolute direction of motion of the earth and the direction of light show different light speeds superimposed, so it is necessary to repeat many experiments at different times. However, it should be noted that the rotation speed of the experimental device should be the same in each experiment.

而实验装置的具体参数（如，转速、挡板 b 到反光镜 c 之间的距离等）则可以根据具体情况来做相应的调整。

The specific parameters of the experimental device (such as the rotation speed, the distance between the baffle b and the mirror c, etc.) can be adjusted accordingly according to the specific situation.

由于每一次实验，其实验装置的转速也许不能完全做到相同，最后就会导致出现一定的测量误差，所以这里就必须在原先实验装置的基础之上，进行了一定的改进。

In each experiment, the speed of the experimental device may not be exactly the same, which will eventually lead to a certain measurement error, so some improvements must be made on the basis of the original experimental device.

2 改进后的实验装置

2 of the improved experimental setup

2.1 改进后的实验装置原理示意图

2.1 The schematic diagram of the improved experimental device

改进之后的光速和“以太”测量装置，可以从方向相反的两边发射光线，当转轴同步转动之后，如果光的速度不存在速度叠加的话，反光镜 c 与投射点 e 之间的连接线，就会与反光镜 c1 与投射点 e1 之间的连接线平行。如果光的速度存在速度叠加的话，则二者之间就会存在一定的夹角，夹角越大就说明来自不同方向的光速差值越大。

The improved speed of light and the ether measuring device can emit light from both sides of the opposite direction. When the rotating shaft rotates synchronously, if the speed of the light is not superimposed, the connecting line between the mirror c and the projection point e will be parallel to the connecting line between the mirror c1 and the projection point e1. If the speed of light is speed superposition, there will be a certain Angle between the two, the larger the Angle, the greater the difference of light from different directions.

反应到实际实验中的话，就是在不同的时间做实验，投射点 e 和投射点 e1 之间，会根

据实验时间和光源方向的变化，而出现微弱的移动。

In the actual experiment, the experiment at different times is weakly changed between the projection point e and e1 according to the experimental time and the direction of the light source.

改进之后的光速和“以太”测量装置，不仅可以测量来自不同方向的单程光速是否存在差异，也可以通过测量出来的结果确定是否存在“以太”，以及根据三元平衡定律的理论推导，来验证地球在宇宙空间是否存在绝对运动，以及绝对运动的方向和大小等等。

Improve the speed of light and "etheric" measurement device, can not only measure from different direction of one light whether there is difference, also can measure the results to determine whether there is "etheric", and according to the theory of the law of ternary balance, to verify whether the earth in space, and the direction of the absolute movement and size, and so on.

2.2 本实验装置的不足之处

2.2 The shortcomings of this experimental setup

本实验装置其实同样存在一个的不足之处，这就是由于这个光速本身非常快，因此这个实验装置测量出的结果可能会非常微弱，实验结果甚至不容易被察觉。也就是，投射点 e 和投射点 e1 之间，会随着实验时间和光源方向的变化，而出现的移动变化非常微弱。

In fact, this experimental device also has a deficiency, which is, because the speed of light itself is very fast, so the measured results of the experimental device may be very weak, and the experimental results are not even easy to detect. That is, the movement between the projection e and e1 changes with the experimental time and the direction of the light source is very weakly.

所以我们就需要对本实验装置进行再一次的优化，而这次的优化的思路，主要是如何将实验的结果放大。

Therefore, we need to optimize this experimental device again, and the idea of this optimization is mainly about how to enlarge the results of the experiment.

2.3 对实验装置的进一步优化

通过增加一个与转轴平行的圆柱形反光镜，如果不同方向的光速不相同的话，那么两束光线经过反光镜 c 和 c1 之后，就不会再保持平行，所以当两束光线照射到与转轴平行的圆柱形反光镜之后，就会将两束光线的角度差放大。

By adding a cylindrical mirror parallel to the rotating axis, if the speed of light in different directions is different, then the two rays of light will not remain parallel after the mirror c and c1, so when the two beams of light illuminate the cylindrical mirror parallel to the rotating axis, the Angle difference between the two rays will be amplified.

同理，我们还可以通过增加与转轴平行的圆柱形反光镜的数量，来对两束光线的角度差进一步放大。

Similarly, we can also further enlarge the angular difference between the two rays by increasing the number of cylindrical mirrors parallel to the rotating axis.

由于本实验装置，主要是用来验证不同方向的单程光速是否相同，而（绝对空间存在的话）单程光速就会随着地球的运动状态发生变化。所以本实验可以在完全相同的实验条件下，不同时间多次实验，如果多次所以的结果存在变化的话，那么就说明“不同方向的单程光速存在差异”，同样也就证明“以太”（绝对空间）存在。

Because this experimental device is mainly used to verify whether the speed of light in different directions is the same, and (if absolute space exists) the speed of light will change with the motion of the earth. Therefore, this experiment can be conducted many times in different times under the same experimental conditions at different times. If the results change many times, it means that "there is a difference in the speed of one-way light in different directions", which also proves the existence of "ether" (absolute space).

2.4 结论

2.4 Conclusion

这套实验装置不仅仅可以用来验证单程光速是否相同，还可以通过相应结果来证明“以太”（绝对空间）是否存在。如果一旦验证“以太”（绝对空间）存在的话，还可以利用这个

装置通过一系列的测量之后，测算出地球在宇宙空间中的绝对速度大小（测量精度足够高的话，理论上可行），最后根据这些测算出来的数据，来验证《三元平衡定律》这本书中相关的理论推导。例如，验证对导致地球磁极位置变化的理论推导等等。

The experimental device can not only be used to verify that the speed of light is the same, but also to prove the existence of "Ether" (absolute space). If once verified "ether" (absolute space), you can also use this device through a series of measurements, measure the absolute speed of the earth in space size (measuring accuracy is high enough, theoretically feasible), finally according to the measured data, to verify the law of ternary balance related theory derivation in the book. For example, to verify the theoretical derivation of the changes in the position of the earth's magnetic poles and so on.

3 结语

3 Conclusion

本文中的“以太”并非传统意义上的一种作为电磁波传播介质的叫做以太的物质，而是一种“绝对静止空间的绝对参考系”。而验证“绝对参考系”的存在与否，则直接影响着未来科学的发展方向。

The "Ether" in this paper is not a matter called Eether in the traditional sense as a medium of electromagnetic wave propagation, but an "absolute reference frame of absolute stationary space". The existence or not of the "absolute reference frame" directly affects the development direction of the future science.

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